

DYNAMIC AXIAL CRUSH OF AUTOMOTIVE RAIL-SIZED COMPOSITE TUBES

PART 3: BRAIDED VS. WOVEN REINFORCEMENTS

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SUMMARY: This paper contrasts dynamic axial crush test results for weave and for braid reinforced automotive rail-sized composite tubes. Reinforcements were made principally of carbon fiber but also Kevlar[®] and E-glass and hybrid combinations of these three. Tubes were manufactured using Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) with processing and molding techniques that are suitable for the low cost high volume needs of the automotive industry. In total 134 dynamic axial crush tests were conducted of 88.9x88.9 mm tubes with 2.54 mm thick walls. A 45° bevel on the lead end of each tube served as the crush initiator. Common to braids and weaves was that consistent and desirable dynamic axial crush response was demonstrated for almost all parameter configurations. Additionally, hybridization of carbon with Kevlar[®] was found to not be necessary for producing stable crush but did prove to be a useful tool for changing crush force levels and increasing post crush integrity. While exceptions existed for particular weaves and braids, those tubes reinforced with weaves had on the average superior energy absorption capabilities compared to those made with braids. This bias may in part be attributable to the much greater use of small fiber bundle aerospace grade fiber products for the weaves than for the braids. Additionally, while exceptions again existed, the ratios of peak to average values of crush force ($F_p/F_{av}(D)$) for braids were, on the average, higher and thus less desirable than those for weaves.

KEYWORDS: dynamic axial crush, composite crush tube, RTM, weave, braid

INTRODUCTION/BACKGROUND

The comparison presented in this paper of the crush responses of tubes with weave and with braid reinforcements made principally from carbon fiber was part of a multi-aspect crush tube program [1, 2] which was initiated to assess the energy absorption characteristics of automotive-sized, liquid composite molded, primarily carbon fiber reinforced tubes. The goal of the program as a whole was to identify combinations of parameters – resin system, fiber reinforcement material type (carbon, Kevlar[®], and E-glass) and architecture, etc. – that will produce stable, progressive dynamic crush. Crush force was desired to be reasonably constant after crush initiation with the crush initiation force sufficiently low so as to avoid failure of the backup structure.

Important drivers for the overall study were i) the lack of published studies of the crush response of advanced fiber reinforced automotive rail-sized tubes made with processing and manufacturing techniques suitable for the automotive industry, ii) the lack of predictive analytical models for the crush response of such tubes [3, 4], and iii) concerns about the suitability of crush debris from such tubes [5].

CRUSH TUBE TEST SPECIMENS

Tube Geometry

An 88.9x88.9 mm square cross section, 460 mm long hollow tube was selected for the present study as being representative of a typical automotive-sized lower rail. Wall thickness was fixed at 2.54 mm for all tubes based on molding considerations and the drive for mass reduction. The exterior radius at the corners was selected to be 12.7 mm, based on previous tests [6, 7].

Molding Approach, Resin System, and Fiber Reinforcement

RTM was selected as the molding approach because of positive experiences with this liquid composite molding (LCM) process in both flat plaque and tube molding trials. Dow Derakane 470 epoxy novolac-based vinylester resin with a glass transition temperature of 155° C was selected based on lower cost as compared to aerospace grade epoxy resin systems, compatibility with fiber sizings and with the desired molding cycles, and high temperature performance.

One of the major intents of the overall program was to characterize the effect of the fiber reinforcement, principally carbon fiber, on the dynamic axial crush response for automotive rail-sized composite tubes. Information on the 10 weaves and 14 braids used in this program are listed in Table 1. All braids came in the form of tubular sock-like material that was dimensioned to fit snugly on our 83.8 mm square Al mandrel. These braids were made variously from carbon, Kevlar[®], E-Glass, and hybrid material combinations. Carbon braids included a lower cost 48k Fortafil carbon fiber tow from Akzo Nobel specially sized for compatibility with vinylester resin systems. The 6 and 12k carbon fiber tows that were used were aerospace grade materials sized for epoxy resin systems. The weaves, as well as the fiberglass veil and CSM were purchased as rolls of fabric. All of the woven carbon fiber products were made from standard 3k aerospace grade carbon fiber tows sized for epoxy resin systems as there were no 48k tow or higher carbon weaves available at the time this study was performed.

Preforming Protocol

Metal (aluminum) mandrels rather than foam cores were used because of their higher thermal expansion coefficient, the latter contributing to higher fiber volume percentages and ease of mandrel removal after molding. Weaves, in general were spiral wrapped about the mandrel. Braided reinforcements, in the form of continuous tubular “sock-like” material, were simply pulled onto the mandrel and snugged into place one layer at a time. One issue arose with braids involving 48k tows. Thicknesses of individual plies of both the bi-axial and tri-axial braids made exclusively with 48k tows were greater than half the 2.54 mm wall thickness of the tubes. Only one ply of these fabrics could thus be used because of the fixed value of wall thickness in our study. An obvious way to work around this issue would be to adjust the part section thickness so as to match (and thus accommodate) multiples of the ply thickness. The constraint of a fixed wall thickness in the present study precluded using this approach. To explore a possible means of working around this issue in a case with fixed wall thickness, we included three constructions in which a second thinner braided ply of lower tow count was added over the 48k tow ply.

Table 1: Fabric Reinforcements for Tube Molding				
Material Source	Material Code	Fabric Description	Material Type	Material Details
Certainteed	U750	CSM	E-Glass	1.5 oz
Certainteed	U750	CSM	E-Glass	2 oz
Hexcel	282	Plain Weave (pw)	Carbon (C)	3k tow
Hexcel	3733	pw	E-Glass	37 1/0
Hexcel	584	8 harness satin (HS)	Carbon	3k tow
Hexcel	613	5HS	Carbon	3k tow
Hexcel	120	pw	Kevlar [®] (K)	195 de
Hexcel	500	pw	Kevlar [®]	1420 de
Hexcel	900	5HS	Kevlar [®]	2160 de
Hexcel	XC-1169	Twill	Carbon/Kevlar [®]	3k/2160 de, both 0° and 90°
Hexcel	XC-790	pw	Carbon/Kevlar [®]	3k C 0°, 2160 de K 90°
Hexcel	716-38	pw	Carbon/E-Glass	3k C 0°, 75 1/0 E-Glass 90°
A&P	GM2056	tri-axial braid 0°±30°	Carbon	6k tow
A&P	GM2082	tri-axial braid 0°±30°	Carbon	12k tow
A&P	GM2086	tri-axial braid 0°±30°	Carbon	48k tow
A&P	GM2081	tri-axial braid 0°±45°	Carbon	12k tow
A&P	GM2084	tri-axial braid 0° _{48k} ±45° _{12k}	Carbon	48k tow (0°), 12k tow (±45°)
A&P	GM2083	tri-axial braid 0° _{48k} ±60° _{12k}	Carbon	48k tow (0°), 12k tow (±60°)
A&P	GM6.00	bi-axial braid ±28°	Carbon	6k tow
A&P	GH6.00	bi-axial braid ±28°	Carbon	12k tow
A&P	GM2085	bi-axial braid ±30°	Carbon	48k tow
A&P	Y24L6-827	bi-axial braid ±28°	E-Glass	E-Glass
A&P	AH6.00	bi-axial braid ±28°	Kevlar [®]	4x1420 de
A&P	AGH6.00	bi-axial braid ±28°	Carbon/Kevlar [®]	12k C, 4x1420 de K
A&P	RGH6.00	bi-axial braid ±28°	Carbon/E-Glass	12k C, 450 E-Glass
A&P	V56L4-12k	bi-axial braid ±45°	Carbon	12k tow

Dynamic Axial Crush Tests

Dynamic axial crush tests were conducted using the GM R&D Center drop tower facility. Detailed information on drop tower testing can be found in [8]. Conditions common to the majority of the tests were as follows:

Crush tube: 88.9x88.9 mm x 460 mm, 2.54 mm thick wall;

Crush initiator: 45° bevel outside edge lead end of tube

Drop mass: 142.9 kg; Drop height: 5.08 m; Impact velocity: 10.0 m/s

Mean crush force, Fav(D), as used here, is the displacement average value of the crush force. SEA (kJ/kg) is defined here as the net energy dissipated in the process of crushing the test

specimen divided by the product of the maximum crush distance and the average mass per unit length of the tube.

In all 134 dynamic axial crush tests were performed. Sixty-three were of tubes with woven reinforcements and 71 of tubes with braided reinforcements with at least two “identical” tests being conducted of each reinforcement architecture.

STUDY FINDINGS

All observations made here pertain specifically to just the dynamic axial crush response, using a 45° bevel crush initiator, of automotive rail-size composite tubes with a square cross section and 2.54 mm wall thickness manufactured using processing and molding techniques (RTM) suitable for the low cost high volume needs of the automotive industry.

Weaves and Braids: Common Features of Crush Response

Crush responses of weave and braid reinforced tubes were found to have several important common features.

First, for both weave and braid reinforcements, consistent and desirable dynamic axial crush response was found for almost all parameter configurations, i.e., stable and progressive crush with a reasonably flat plateau force level and an acceptable initial peak/crush initiation force, i.e. one that can be withstood by the backup structure. The only exceptions were the CSM constructions, which required the use of a plug-type initiator to produce stable progressive crush. Typical crush force versus crush traces for tests of tubes reinforced with weaves and with braids, respectively, illustrating these desirable response features are shown in Figs. 1a and 1b.

Fig. 1a. Crush Force vs. Crush (Weave)

Fig. 1b. Crush Force vs. Crush (Braid)

Second, for both weave and braid reinforcements, the inclusion of Kevlar® in the reinforcement, either by itself or in combination with carbon, was found to dramatically increase the level of post-crush integrity. This was not the case with the inclusion of E-glass. Crush morphologies for all the reinforcement architectures are listed in Tables 4 and 5, the two basic crush morphologies that were observed in the tests with a 45° bevel as initiator being tearing in the longitudinal direction along the four corners of the square tubes into four relatively straight and stiff fronds

and a progressive accordion folding of the walls. Photographs of dynamically crushed tubes that exhibited these two dramatically different crush morphologies are shown Fig. 2.

(a) Corner Tearing Mode

(b) "Accordion Mode"

Fig. 2. Two Basic Crush Morphologies for Square Tubes - 45° Bevel Crush Initiator

These morphologies either occurred in pure form or as a blend of the two depending on the fiber architecture and material. It is to be noted that for all tubes tested stiffness of the crushed portions under either bending or axial compressive loads was dramatically reduced.

Third, hybridization of carbon with Kevlar® and/or glass, both of which have higher failure strains, in both weave and braid architectures was found unnecessary for producing stable crush but did prove to be a useful tool for changing crush modes and force levels.

Weaves and Braids: Differences in Crush Response

The present study also identified numerous important differences between the crush responses of weave and braid reinforced tubes.

Fav(D) and SEA

The data on Fav(D) and SEA for weave and for braid reinforced tubes for dynamic axial crush tests conducted with a 45° bevel crush initiator appear in Tables 2 and 3, respectively.

In terms of Fav(D), 5 of the 7 values greater than 25 kN were for weaves. In terms of SEA, weaves again had the majority of higher values, having 8 of the 11 values greater than 20 kJ/kg. In general, while exceptions existed for particular weave and braid architectures, those tubes reinforced with weaves had on the average superior energy absorption compared to those made with braids. This bias may in part be attributable to the much greater use of small fiber bundle aerospace grade fiber products for the weaves than for the braids. Unfortunately, while we were able to get a commercial braider to experiment with and ultimately produce both bi-axial and tri-axial braids for us with 48k tows, during the 1995-96 time frame of this study we were unable to procure any weaves based on such large carbon fiber tows.

In terms of best and worst, for weaves, the (3k C,K both direct., twill)₆ construction molded at 60°C had the highest values, 30.70 kN and 27.54 kJ/kg respectively, in terms of both SEA and Fav(D). The two woven reinforcement configurations for which the lowest values of both measures were recorded were 2*[(CSM/(0°,90°) 3k pw], 90°C and 3*[(CSM/(0°,90°) 3k pw], 90°C) involving alternating layers of CSM and 3k pw carbon. For braids, (±28°)₄, 6k had the highest values, 26.51 kN and 22.44 kJ/kg, and the (0°-48k C, ±30° 12k G)₂ hybrid tri-axial braid construction had the lowest at 11.88 kN and 10.42 kJ/kg.

Construction	Fav(D) (kN) (non-plug)	SEA (kJ/kg) (non-plug)	Std Dev Fav(D) (kN)	Std Dev (SEA) (kJ/kN)
(3k C,K both direct., twill) ₆ , 60°C	30.70	27.54	2.86	2.88
(0°,90°) ₉ 3k pw, 90°C	28.85	23.95	4.91	4.11
(3k C,K both direct., twill) ₅ , 60°C	24.99	23.15		
(0°,90°) ₈ 3k pw, 90°C	26.32	22.58	4.78	3.86
(0°,90°) ₈ 3k pw, 60°C	25.14	22.02	2.93	3.74
[Pl. Weave C(0,3k),K(90)] ₇ , 90°C	24.38	21.74	1.42	1.39
(0°,90°) ₉ 3k pw, 60°C	24.60	21.15	3.35	3.75
[Pl. Weave C(0,3k),G(90)] ₁₂ , 90°C	25.31	20.36	3.19	2.72
[5HS(6k)] ₅ , 90°C	21.95	18.82	3.24	2.25
(0°,90°) ₁₀ 3k pw, 60°C	19.96	18.82	9.26	7.71
4*[(3733(G)(0°,90°) pw)/(0°,90°)(C) 3k pw], 90°C	20.36	17.59		
2*[(CSM/(0°,90°) 3k pw], 90°C	15.78	14.57		
SPIRAL-3*[(CSM/(0°,90°) 3k pw], 90°C	16.67	13.71		

Braid Configuration	Fav(D) (kN) (Non-Plug)	SEA (kJ/kg) (Non-Plug)	Std Dev Fav(D) (kN)	Std Dev SEA (kJ/kg)
(±28°) ₄ , 6k	26.51	22.44	4.34	3.02
(±28°) ₃ Kevlar®	20.23	18.48	0.62	0.35
(±45°) ₃ , 12k	21.28	18.46	1.40	1.09
(±28°) ₃ , 12k	20.58	17.74	1.52	0.82
(±28°) ₃ 12k C/K	20.17	17.61	1.60	1.17
(±30°) ₁ , 48k	20.18	17.48	1.00	0.53
(±28°) ₄ , 12k glass	20.81	16.16	1.67	3.05
(±28°) ₃ 12k C/G	19.97	15.17	1.19	0.62
(±28°) ₃ , 12k glass	18.03	13.88	0.96	0.92
(0°±30°) ₃ , 12k	24.70	20.89	2.55	2.14
(0°±30°) ₃ , 6k	20.66	19.37	0.00	0.00
(0°-48k, ±45°-12k) ₂	22.38	18.89	1.54	1.29
(0°-48k, ±45°-12k) ₁	20.21	18.45	0.81	0.44
(0°±30°) ₂ , 12k	20.04	18.33	3.05	2.58
(0°±45°) ₂ , 12k	21.83	18.28	3.13	1.07
(0°-48k, ±60°-12k) ₁	18.10	16.73	1.66	1.53
(0°±30°) ₃ , 6k, 60°C	18.20	16.49	1.98	1.77
(0°±30°) ₁ , 48k	16.37	14.71	2.49	2.15
(0°-48k C, ±30° 12k G) ₁	16.22	14.27	1.19	1.11
(0°±30°) ₁ , 12k	12.44	12.21	1.36	1.26
(0°-48k C, ±30° 12k G) ₂	11.88	10.42	5.02	4.17
(±28°, 12k)/(±30°, 48k)	25.06	20.33	5.24	4.09
(±28°, 12k)/(0°±30°, 48k)	22.52	18.94	2.17	1.90
(0°±30°, 12k)/(0°±30°, 48k)	18.89	15.99	1.21	0.97

Ratio of F_p to $F_{av}(D)$

Fig. 3. Woven Fiber Architectures: Ratio of F_p to $F_{av}(D)$ - 45° Bevel Crush Initiator

Fig. 4. Braided Fiber Architectures: Ratio of F_p to $F_{av}(D)$ - 45° Bevel Crush Initiator

Ratios of F_p to $F_{av}(D)$, which are desired to be as close as possible to 1.0 for automotive applications, are presented for weave and braid reinforced tubes in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively.

The ratios for braids are, on the average, seen to be higher, making braids, on the average, less desirable from this standpoint.

Crush Morphology

Table 4: Woven Fabrics: Crush Morphologies in Dynamic Axial Crush	
Construction	Crush Morphology
(CSM) ₃ , 60°C	Buckled
(0°,90°) ₈ 3k pw, 60°C	tore at corners
(0°,90°) ₈ 3k pw, 90°C	tore at corners
(0°,90°) ₉ 3k pw, 60°C	mixed corner tearing and accordion
(0°,90°) ₉ 3k pw, 90°C	mixed corner tearing and accordion
(0°,90°) ₁₀ 3k pw, 60°C	corner tears (outer)+ accordion (inner)
SPIRAL-3*[(CSM/(0°,90°) 3k pw], 90°C	tore at corners
2*[(CSM/(0°,90°) 3k pw], 90°C	tore at corners
4*[(3733(G)(0°,90°) pw)/(0°,90°)(C) 3k pw], 90°C	corner tears (outer)+ accordion (inner)
(3k C,K both direct., twill) ₆ , 60°C	accordion
(3k C,K both direct., twill) ₅ , 60°C	pure accordion
[5HS(6k)] ₅ , 90°C	tore at corners
[Pl. Weave C(0,3k),K(90)] ₇ , 90°C	predominately accordion
[Pl. Weave C(0,3k),G(90)] ₁₂ , 90°C	corner tears (outer)+ accordion (inner)

Crush morphologies observed for the woven reinforcement architectures for a 45° bevel crush initiator are listed above in Table 4. It is important to note that these crush morphologies are specific to the woven configurations used in this study which were all (0°,90°) weaves aligned with warps parallel to the tube axis. Table 5 listed the crush morphologies observed for the braided architectures for a 45° bevel crush initiator. The same types and range of morphologies are seen to have been produced by both weaves and braids. Corner tearing was the more dominant mode for the weaves except for the carbon/ Kevlar® hybrids. Corner tearing was also the dominant mode for the tri-axial braids. In contrast, for the bi-axial braids an accordion folding pattern was the dominant mode with only the 6k braid exhibiting major corner tearing.

Fiber Material

Considering first the weaves, referring to Tables 2 and 4 and Fig. 3, woven fabrics with a combination of carbon and Kevlar® produced in general higher values of both SEA and Fav(D), lower ratios of Fp/Fav(D), and superior crush morphologies. In contrast, woven fabrics with a combination of both carbon and E-glass had lower values of both SEA and Fav(D), higher ratios of Fp/Fav(D), and inferior crush morphologies. Comparing weaves with just carbon to those with hybrid combinations of Kevlar® and carbon, superior performance was obtained when Kevlar® was included along with carbon in the weaves in both the 0° and 90° directions.

Considering next the braided reinforcements, referring to Tables 3 and 5 and Fig. 4, the material of the off-axis tows is seen to have had no significant effect on Fav(D). However, values of SEA varied inversely with the fiber material density making Kevlar® the material of choice for use in bi-axial braids and in the off-axis tows in tri-axial braids. In contrast, E-glass was the worst performer in these applications.

Thus, in general, though hybridization of carbon with Kevlar[®] was not necessary for producing stable crush in tubes reinforced with weaves and braids, it did improve SEA levels and increase post crush integrity in contrast to opposite effects found for hybridization with E-glass.

Construction	Crush Morphology
(±28°) ₄ , 6k	mostly tearing at corners, some accordion
(±45°) ₃ , 12k	close to pure accordion
(±28°) ₃ , 12k	mostly accordion, 1 frond peeled out
(±30°) ₁ , 48k	either mostly large plate accordion or tight accordion smooching
(±28°) ₃ , 12k glass	pure accordion
(±28°) ₄ , 12k glass	mostly pure accordion
(±28°) ₃ , 12k C/K	pure accordion
(±28°) ₃ Kevlar [®]	pure accordion
(±28°) ₃ , 12k C/G	pure accordion
(0°±30°) ₁ , 48k	tore at corners, some accordion
(0°±30°) ₁ , 12k	tore at corners, fronds chunking in sections
(0°±30°) ₂ , 12k	accordion + corner tearing
(0°±30°) ₃ , 12k	accordion + corner tearing
(0°±30°) ₃ , 6k, 60°C	mostly corner tear
(0°±30°) ₃ , 6k	tore at 4 corners, some accordion
(0°±45°) ₂ , 12k	initial full accordion, then 2 fronds, 2 accordion
(0°-48k, ±45°-12k) ₁	corner tearing, fronds in big chunks
(0°-48k, ±45°-12k) ₂	tore at corners, some accordion
(0°-48k, ±60°-12k) ₁	tore at corners
(0°-48k C, ±30° 12k G) ₁	tore at corners, 2 fronds in
(0°-48k C, ±30° 12k G) ₂	tore at corners, some large plate accordion
(±28°, 12k)/(0°±30°, 48k)	accordion last 2/3
(±28°, 12k)/(±30°, 48k)	mostly corner tearing, some accordion
(0°±30°, 12k)/(0°±30°, 48k)	corner tearing + accordion

Summary/Conclusions

A comparison was made of the dynamic axial crush responses of weave and braid reinforced automotive rail-sized square cross section composite tubes that were reinforced principally with carbon fiber but also Kevlar[®] and E-glass and hybrid combinations of these three, and that had been manufactured using Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) with processing and molding techniques that are suitable for the low cost high volume needs of the automotive industry. Altogether, 134 dynamic axial crush tests were performed using a 45° bevel as the crush initiator. Note in particular that tube wall thickness was fixed at a single value, 2.54 mm, in this study.

Important findings were as follows:

- For both weave and braid reinforcements, consistent and desirable dynamic axial crush response was found for all reinforcement architectures except CSM, i.e., stable and progressive

crush with a reasonably flat plateau force level and an acceptable initial peak/crush initiation force, i.e. one that can be withstood by the backup structure.

- The inclusion of Kevlar[®] in the reinforcement, either by itself or in combination with carbon, was found to dramatically increase the level of post-crush integrity. This was not the case with the inclusion of E-glass.
- Hybridization of carbon with either Kevlar[®] or E-glass was not necessary for producing stable crush but did prove to be a useful tool for changing force levels and post crush integrity.
- While exceptions existed, as a group those tubes reinforced with weaves had on the average superior energy absorption capabilities compared to those made with braids. This bias may in part, however, be attributable to the much greater use of small fiber bundle aerospace grade fiber products for the weaves than for the braids.
- While exceptions again existed, the ratios of $F_p/F_{av}(D)$ for braids were, on the average, higher and thus less desirable for automotive applications than those for weaves.
- The two basic crush morphologies observed in tests conducted with a 45° bevel crush initiator were tearing in the longitudinal direction along the four corners of the square tubes into four relatively straight and stiff fronds and a progressive accordion folding of the walls. These morphologies either occurred in pure form or as a blend of the two depending on the fiber architecture and material. Tubes with bi-axial braid reinforcement were more likely to produce an accordion crush morphology than either tri-axial braids or weaves.
- In tubes with both braid and weave reinforcements, when combinations of reinforcement materials were used, SEA was highest and $F_p/F_{av}(D)$ lowest when Kevlar was used in combination with carbon. In contrast, the lowest values of SEA and highest values of $F_p/F_{av}(D)$ occurred when E-glass was used in combination with carbon.

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